

ON THE M -POWER COMPLEMENT NUMBERS

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the asymptotic properties of the m -power complement numbers, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it.

§1. Introduction and results

Let $n \geq 2$ is any integer, $a_m(n)$ is called a m -power complement about n if $a_m(n)$ is the smallest integer such that $n \times a_m(n)$ is a perfect m -power. For example $a_m(2) = 2^{m-1}$, $a_m(3) = 3^{m-1}$, $a_m(4) = 2^{m-2}$, $a_m(2^m) = 1, \dots$. The famous Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as following:

$$S(n) = \min\{m : m \in N, n \mid m!\}.$$

For example, $S(1) = 1$, $S(2) = 2$, $S(3) = 3$, $S(4) = 4$, $S(5) = 5$, $S(6) = 3, \dots$. In reference [1], Professor F.Smarandache asked us to study the properties of m -power complement number sequence. About this problem, some authors have studied it before. See [4]. In this paper, we use the elementary method to study the mean value properties of m -power complement number sequence, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. Let $x \geq 1$ be any real number and $m \geq 2$, then we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} a_m(S(n)) = \frac{x^m \zeta(m)}{m \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^m}{\ln^2 x}\right).$$

§2. Proof of the theorem

To complete the proof of the theorem, we need some lemmas.

Lemma 1. If $p(n) > \sqrt{n}$, then $S(n) = p(n)$.

Proof. Let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} p(n)$; so we have

$$n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} < \sqrt{n}$$

then

$$p_i^{\alpha_i} \mid p(n)!, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r.$$

So $n \mid p(n)!$, but $p(n) \nmid (p(n) - 1)!$, so $S(n) = p(n)$.

This completes the proof of the lemma 1.

Lemma 2. *If $x \geq 1$ be any real number and $m \geq 2$, then we have the two asymptotic formulae:*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p(n) \leq \sqrt{n}}} S^{m-1}(n) = O\left(x^{\frac{m+1}{2}} \ln^{m-1} x\right);$$

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p(n) > \sqrt{n}}} S^{m-1}(n) = \frac{x^m \zeta(m)}{m \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^m}{\ln^2 x}\right).$$

Proof. First, from the Euler summation formula [2] we can easily get

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p(n) \leq \sqrt{n}}} S^{m-1}(n) \ll \sum_{n \leq x} (\sqrt{n} \ln n)^{m-1} \\ &= \int_1^x (\sqrt{t} \ln t)^{m-1} dt + \int_1^x (t - [t]) \left((\sqrt{t} \ln t)^{m-1} \right)' dt + (\sqrt{x} \ln x)^{m-1} (x - [x]) \\ &= \frac{m+3}{m+1} x^{\frac{m+1}{2}} \ln^{m-1} x + O\left(x^{\frac{m}{2}} \ln^{m-1} x\right). \end{aligned}$$

And then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p(n) > \sqrt{n}}} S^{m-1}(n) &= \sum_{\substack{np \leq x \\ p > \sqrt{np}}} S^{m-1}(np) = \sum_{\substack{n \leq \sqrt{x} \\ \sqrt{n} < p \leq \frac{x}{n}}} p^{m-1} \\ &= \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{\sqrt{n} < p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p^{m-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $\pi(x)$ denote the number of the primes up to x . From [3], we have

$$\pi(x) = \frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right).$$

Using Abel's identity [2], we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\sqrt{x} < p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p^{m-1} &= \pi\left(\frac{x}{n}\right) \left(\frac{x}{n}\right)^{m-1} - \pi(\sqrt{x}) (\sqrt{x})^{m-1} - \int_{\sqrt{x}}^{\frac{x}{n}} \pi(t) (t^{m-1})' dt \\ &= \left(\frac{x^m}{n^m (\ln x - \ln n)} + O\left(\frac{x^m}{n^m (\ln x - \ln n)^2}\right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - \left(\frac{2x^{\frac{m}{2}}}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{4x^{\frac{m}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right) \right) - (m-1) \int_{\sqrt{x}}^{\frac{x}{\sqrt{x}}} \left(\frac{t^{m-1}}{\ln t} + O\left(\frac{t^{m-1}}{\ln^2 x}\right) \right) dt \\
 & = \frac{x^m}{mn^m \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^m}{n^m \ln^2 x}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

According to [2], we know that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{1}{n^s} = \frac{x^{1-s}}{1-s} + \zeta(s) + O(x^{-s}) \quad \text{if } s > 0, s \neq 1.$$

so we have

$$\sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{\sqrt{n} < p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p^{m-1} = \frac{x^m \zeta(m)}{m \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^m}{\ln^2 x}\right).$$

This completes the proof of the lemma 2.

3 Proof of the Theorem

In this section, we complete the proof of the Theorem. Combining Lemma 1, Lemma 2 and the definition of $a_m(n)$ it is clear that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n \leq x} a_m(S(n)) & = \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p(n) > \sqrt{n}}} p^{m-1} + O\left(\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p(n) \leq \sqrt{n}}} (\sqrt{n} \ln n)^{m-1} \right) \\
 & = \frac{x^m \zeta(m)}{m \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^m}{\ln^2 x}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the Theorem.

Acknowledgments

The author express his gratitude to his supervisor Professor Zhang Wenpeng for his very helpful and detailed instructions.

References

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